

Development and Validation of a Robust RP-HPLC Method for Quantitative Estimation of Selexipag in Tablet Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

This study presents the development and validation of a reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for the analysis of Selexipag, a selective prostacyclin receptor agonist used in the treatment of pulmonary arterial hypertension. The method employed a Phenomenex ODS 3 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μ m) with an isocratic mobile phase composed of acetonitrile and 0.05% orthophosphoric acid in water (85:15, v/v) at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min, and a column temperature of 35°C. Detection was carried out using a UV detector set at 298 nm. The RP-HPLC method was optimized to achieve a retention time of 2.95 minutes with a total run time of 6 minutes, enabling effective separation and accurate quantification of Selexipag. Method validation, conducted in accordance with International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines, demonstrated excellent linearity ($R^2 = 0.99998$), precision (%RSD < 2%), accuracy (recovery 98–102%), specificity, solution stability up to 24 hours, and robustness. Selexipag was characterized as a white, odourless, crystalline powder, and was found to be soluble in methanol but not in water. This validated RP-HPLC method offers a reliable, precise, and sensitive approach for routine quality control and pharmaceutical research involving Selexipag formulations. It supports regulatory compliance and has potential applications in pharmacokinetic and stability studies

Keywords: Selexipag, RP-HPLC, Method development, Method validation, ICH Q2(R1) guidelines, Pharmaceutical analysis, Pulmonary arterial hypertension, Prostacyclin receptor agonist, Quality control, Tablet formulation.

INTRODUCTION

Selexipag (brand name Upravi) is a drug developed by Actelion [1]. Selexipag is pale yellow coloured crystalline substance having chemical name 2-{4-[5,6-diphenylpyrazin-2-yl](propan-2-yl)amino]butoxy}-N-methanesulfonyl acetamide. It

is a pharmacological agent that can be taken orally and selectively targets the prostacyclin receptor, acting as an agonist. Food and Drug Administration approved SLP in 2015 for the treatment of pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH) in patients with functional class II or III [2].

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

SLP has the molecular formula C₂₆H₃₂N₄O₄S and a molecular weight of 496.63 g/mol. SLP appears as a light yellow crystalline powder that is nearly insoluble in water [3]. Statistical parameters like mean, mode, standard deviation were used to analyse the obtained data and draw suitable conclusions based on their results [4,5]. Further improvements in method optimization and system suitability parameters should be made in line with ICH (Q2) R1 guidelines [6].

Mechanism of Selexipag is a selective prostacyclin (IP, also called PGI₂) receptor agonist. The key features of pulmonary arterial hypertension include a decrease in prostacyclin and prostacyclin synthase (enzyme that helps produce prostacyclin) in the lung. Prostacyclin is a potent vasodilator with anti-proliferative, anti-inflammatory, and anti-thrombotic [7].

Fig. Chemical Structure of Selexipag

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and Reagents: Selexipag was collected as a drug sample for research purposes. The Selepeg 0.4 mg Tablet was purchased from a nearby store.

Instrumentation and Chromatographic Conditions: Chromatographic separation was performed isocratically using a Phenomenex ODS 3 (250 mm X 4.6 mm i.d.) with a 5 µm mobile phase composition of a mixture of acetonitrile and water (85:15) at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and a sample injection of 20 µL was injected. The eluent was monitored with a UV detector set at 298 nm. The diluent was a mixture of acetonitrile and water (85:15).

Preparation of the mobile phase: The mobile phase consists of Acetonitrile and 0.05% orthophosphoric acid in water in a ratio of (85:15). The solution was filtered through a 0.45-µ (Nylon syringe) membrane

filter. This solution was used as a mobile phase for further analysis.

Selection of an analytical wavelength

Selection of solvents:

Methanol was selected as the solvent for dissolving Selexipag.

Preparation of standard solutions for UV scans to determine Absorption maxima wavelength

In order to prepare stock solution, weighed accurately 20 mg Selexipag and transferred into 20 ml volumetric flask, added 15 ml of Methanol and sonicated to dissolve the standard completely and diluted up to the mark with Methanol (1000 PPM).

Further diluted 0.5 mL to 25 mL with Methanol. (20 PPM)

Solution scanned from 400 nm to 200 nm.

Selection of an analytical wavelength

Methanol as a blank and Selexipag standard solution (20 PPM) was scanned from 400 nm to 200 nm. Absorption maxima was determined for drug. 298 nm wavelength used for further analysis.

Method Development by RP – HPLC

Preparation of standard solution for Chromatographic development:

Selexipag Standard stock solution was prepared by dissolving 20 mg Selexipag into a 20 mL clean and dried volumetric flask added about 15 mL of Methanol to dissolve it completely and made volume up to the mark with Methanol (1000 PPM).

Further diluted 2 ml of stock solution to 20 mL with mobile phase (100 PPM). It was prepared in mobile phase of each trial and injected in development trials.

Selection of analytical wavelength for HPLC method development:

Analytical wavelength for the examination was selected from the wavelength of maximum absorption

from the spectrophotometric analysis and it was 298 nm.

Chromatographic Conditions:

Standard solution:	Selexipag 100 PPM
Column:	Phenomenex ODS 3,
Column Dimension:	(250 mm X 4.6 mm i.d.) 5µm
Column oven temp:	35°C
Detector:	U.V. Detector
Wavelength:	298 nm
Flow Rate:	1.0 ml/min
Mobile phase:	Acetonitrile : 0.05% OPA in Water (85:15)
Injection Volume:	20µl

Table No.1. Chromatographic Conditions

Validation of the RP-HPLC Method:

As per the ICH recommendations for the following parameters, the suggested method for the Selexipag estimate was verified.

FILTRATION STUDY:

Filtration study of an analytical procedure checks the interference of extraneous components from filter, deposition on filter bed and compatibility of filter with sample.

This study was conducted with Selexipag Test sample (Tablet solution).

Filtration study carried out with unfiltered and filtered test solution. During filtration activity 0.45 µm PVDF and 0.45 µm Nylon syringe filters used by discarding 5 mL of aliquot sample.

Stability of Analytical Solution:

Stability study was conducted for standard and test sample solution. Stability study was performed at normal laboratory conditions.

The solution was stored at normal illuminated laboratory conditions and analyzed after 12 hours and 24 hours.

Standard and Test solution stability study was performed by calculating the difference between results of test solution at each stability time point to that of initial.

SPECIFICITY:

Specificity is the ability to access unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present.

Following solution shall be prepared and injected to prove the specificity nature of the method.

- I. Blank (Methanol as Blank)
- II. Placebo

Analyzing marketed test sample contains excipients (additives) which are totally unknown. So Placebo prepared at lab level by using formula as follows:

Placebo preparation:

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Role	Qty (mg)
1	Lactose	Filler	80
2	Starch	Binder	5
3	Magnesium stearate	Lubricant	5
4	Talc	Glidant	5
5	crospovidone	Disintegrants	5
Total			100 mg

Table no.2. Placebo preparation

Total 10 gm of placebo prepared

Placebo Sample solution preparation:

Weighed 680.0 mg of placebo material (Which is equivalent to 2 mg of Selexipag) and transferred to clean and dried 50 mL of volumetric flask. Added 35 mL of Methanol, sonicated for 15 minutes with intermittent shaking. After 15 minutes allow to cool the solution to room temperature and made volume up to the mark with Methanol. Filtered the solution through suitable 0.45 μ Nylon syringe filter discarding 3-5 mL of initial filtrate. Further diluted 2.5 ml of filtered stock solution to 20 ml with mobile phase, injected the resultant solution and chromatograms were recorded.

LINEARITY AND RANGE

Sr. No.	Level (%)	mL of stock solution	Diluted to with Mobile phase (mL)	Selexipag Concentration (μ g/mL)
1	10	0.2	20	0.50
2	50	1.0	20	2.50
3	100	2.0	20	5.00
4	125	2.5	20	6.25
5	150	3.0	20	7.50

Table no. 3. Linearity levels prepared**Determination**

Each level injected in triplicate and mean area calculated. Calibration curve was plotted graphically as a function of analyte concentration in μ g/mL on X-axis Vs mean area on y-Axis as given in results.

Preparation of linearity solution

The linearity of an analytical procedure is its ability (within a given range) to obtain test results which are directly proportional to the concentration (amount) of analyte in the sample. 5 levels of Linearity was performed from 10% to 150% of working concentration

Linearity Selexipag stock solution:

Weighed 25 mg of Selexipag and dissolved in 50 mL with Methanol. Further diluted 5.0 ml of stock solution to 50 mL with Methanol (50 μ g/mL).

Linearity levels prepared as follows:**Acceptance criteria**

Correlation Coefficient: NLT 0.98

Intercept: To be report

Slope: To be report

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ):**Detection limit:**

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value.

Quantitation limit:

The quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy.

As per ICH Q2R1 guidelines LOD and LOQ was determined by using the approach Based on the Calibration Curve in which residual standard deviation of a regression line was calculated and determined the LOD and LOQ by using following formula:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \sigma / S$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma / S$$

Where,

σ = residual standard deviation of a regression line

S = Slope of regression line

ACCURACY (% RECOVERY)

The accuracy of the analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between the value which is accepted either as a conventional true value or an accepted reference value and the value of the value found,

Accuracy will be conducted in the range from 50 % to 150 % of working concentration. Solution of each accuracy level was prepared in triplicate. Calculated % Recovery for each sample, Mean % recovery for each level and overall recovery and also calculated % RSD for each level and % RSD for overall recovery.

Accuracy levels details:

Refer Following table for each sample:

Level (%)	Volume Taken (mL)	Placebo	Diluted to (mL)	Volume taken (mL)	Diluted to (mL)	Conc (µg/mL)
50	1.0	680.6	50	2.5	20	2.50
	1.0	679.5	50	2.5	20	2.50
	1.0	680.1	50	2.5	20	2.50
100	2.0	680.8	50	2.5	20	5.00
	2.0	679.9	50	2.5	20	5.00
	2.0	679.4	50	2.5	20	5.00
150	3.0	680.4	50	2.5	20	7.50
	3.0	680.5	50	2.5	20	7.50
	3.0	680.3	50	2.5	20	7.50

Table no.4. Accuracy levels details

Procedure for preparation of Accuracy sample solution:

Take clean and dried 9 volumetric flasks of 50 mL. Weighed approx 680.0 mg of placebo and transferred in each 50 mL volumetric flask. Spiked Selexipag API stock as per accuracy level in same 50 ml volumetric flask. Added 35 ml of Methanol sonicated it for 15 minutes with intermittent shaking. Allowed to cool the solution at room temperature and made the volume up to the mark with Methanol. Filtered the solution through suitable 0.45 μ Nylon filter discarding 5 mL of filtrate. Further diluted 2.5 ml of filtrate to 20 ml with mobile phase.

Acceptance criteria

1. % Recovery for each sample and Mean recovery and overall recovery should be in the range of 98-102%.
2. The Relative Standard Deviation should not be more than 2.0%.

PRECISION

Precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the

same homogeneous test under the prescribed conditions. Precision is of two types, Repeatability and Intermediate precision. It is performed on tablet test sample.

I. Repeatability:

Preparation of sample solution (6 Samples prepared):

Weighed 20 tablets and calculated average weight and transferred in mortar pestle and crushed to fine powder. Mixed the contents with butter paper uniformly. Weighed the powder material equivalent to 2 mg of Selexipag (682.0 mg of powder material) and transferred to clean and dried 50 mL of volumetric flask. Added 35 mL of Methanol, sonicated for 15 minutes with intermittent shaking. After 15 minutes allow to cool the solution to room temperature and made volume up to the mark with Methanol. Filtered the solution through suitable 0.45 μ Nylon syringe filter discarding 3-5 mL of initial filtrate. Further dilute 2.5 ml of filtered stock solution to 20 ml with mobile phase. (5 mcg of Selexipag), injected the resultant solution and chromatograms were recorded.

Six samples prepared.

Precision (Repeatability) Sample details are as follows:

Sample	Powder wt (mg)	Diluted to (mL)	Volume taken (mL)	Diluted to (mL)
Sample 1	682.6	50	2.5	20
Sample 2	683.2	50	2.5	20
Sample 3	682.4	50	2.5	20
Sample 4	682.8	50	2.5	20
Sample 5	683.3	50	2.5	20
Sample 6	682.2	50	2.5	20

Table no.5. Precision (Repeatability) Sample details

Acceptance criteria:

% Assay: 90-110% for each sample and mean assay value

% RSD for % assay value of 6 samples: NMT 2%

II. Intermediate precision

It is performed by doing analysis on another day to check reproducibility of results. Samples prepared in same manner as that of Repeatability parameter (6 Samples prepared).

Intermediate Precision Sample details are as follows:

Sample	Powder wt. (mg)	Diluted to (mL)	Volume taken (mL)	Diluted to (mL)
Sample 1	682.5	50	2.5	20
Sample 2	681.8	50	2.5	20
Sample 3	682.4	50	2.5	20
Sample 4	682.7	50	2.5	20
Sample 5	683.2	50	2.5	20
Sample 6	682.6	50	2.5	20

Table no.6. Intermediate Precision Sample details

Acceptance criteria:

% Assay: 90-110% for each sample and mean assay value

% RSD for % assay of 6 samples of Intermediate precision: NMT 2

% RSD for Total 12 samples: NMT 2% for test results (6 of Repeatability and 6 of Intermediate precision)

ROBUSTNESS

The robustness of an analytical procedure is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small, but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage.

Determination: Standard solution was injected under different chromatographic conditions as shown below.

- Changes in flow rate by $\pm 10\%$. (± 0.1 ml/min)
- Change in column oven temperature. ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$)
- Change in wavelength (± 3 nm)

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Primary Characterization and Identification of Drugs

Color, odor, and appearance of the drug

Sr. No	Name	Colour, odour and appearance of drug
1.	Selexipag	White, odourless and Crystalline powder.

Table no.7. Color, odour, and appearance

Solubility study

Solubility study of Selexipag

Sr. No.	Name of Solvent	Observation	Conclusion	Summary
1	Water	Drug Particles seen after sonication	Drug was not found soluble in water.	Methanol used as a diluent for preparing stock solution.
2	Methanol	No Drug Particles seen after sonication	Drug was found soluble in methanol.	

Table no.8. Solubility study

Selection of solvent:

Methanol was selected as the solvent for dissolving Selexipag.

Selection of analytical wavelength

1) Blank Methanol:

Fig No.1 UV spectrum of Methanol as a blank

2) Selexipag STD solution (20 PPM)

Fig. No. 2 UV spectrum of Selexipag

Observation: The standard solution was scanned from 400 nm to 200 nm. Wavelength of maximum absorption was determined for drug. Selexipag showed maximum absorbance at 298 nm. It is shown

in **Figure No.2**. Therefore 298 nm considered as an analytical wavelength for further determination.

Method Development by RP – HPLC**Optimization of HPLC method**

Trial 1:**Chromatogram:****Fig. No. 3 Typical chromatogram of Trial 1**

Observation: Selexipag eluted with Unacceptable Chromatography. **Conclusion:** Method rejected.

Trial 2:**Chromatogram:****Fig. No. 4 Typical chromatogram of Trial 2**

Observation: Selexipag eluted with unacceptable chromatography. Peak shape not Acceptable (Broad peak). **Conclusion:** Method rejected

Trial 3:**Chromatogram:**

Observation: Selexipag eluted at R.T 5.36 min, with good chromatography. (Asymmetry: 1.16 & Theoretical plate: 10923)

Conclusion: Try to reduce Selexipag R.T by change in mobile phase composition in next trial.

Trial 4:

Chromatogram:

Fig. No. 6 Typical chromatogram of Trial 4

Observation: Selexipag eluted at R.T of 2.95 min, and good chromatography observed. (Asymmetry: 1.24 & Theoretical plate: 11107)

Conclusion: From the observations of trials first to four, it was concluded that chromatographic conditions in trial four gives better peak, good retention time and tailing factor therefore chromatographic conditions in trial four was subjected for validation

Conclusion: Method Accepted.

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

Parameter	Description
Mode	Isocratic
Column Name	Phenomenex ODS 3, 250 mm X 4.6 mm, 5 μ m
Detector	UV Detector
Injection Volume	20 μ l
Wavelength	298 nm
Column Oven temp	35°C
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile : 0.05% OPA in water (85:15)
Flow Rate	1.0 ml/min
Run time	06 minutes
Retention time	2.93min

Table no.9.Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

System suitability test

Results for System Suitability Test of Selexipag

Sr No.	Standard solution	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates
1	Standard_1	5466019	1.22	9539
2	Standard_2	5454506	1.22	9563
3	Standard_3	5484700	1.23	9548
4	Standard_4	5474091	1.22	9557
5	Standard_5	5459413	1.21	9528
Mean		5467746	1.22	9547
STD Dev		11993.91678		
% RSD		0.22		

Table no.10. System Suitability Test

System Suitability Acceptance Criteria:

1. Relative standard deviation of the area of analyte peaks in standard chromatograms should not be more than 2.0 %.
2. Theoretical plates of analyte peak in standard chromatograms should not be less than 2000.

3. Tailing Factor (Asymmetry) of analyte peaks in Standard Chromatograms should be less than 2.0

Data interpretation: It was observed from the data tabulated above; the method complies with system suitability parameters. Hence, it can be concluded that the chromatographic method is adequate for intended analysis.

Sample Name: STANDARD SOLUTION_1

VWD: Signal A,
298 nm Results

Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Selexipag	2.93	5466019	1.22	9539
Totals		5466019		

Fig. No. 7 Typical chromatogram Standard solution 1 of system suitability solution.

Analysis of Marketed Test samples (Assay)**a) Selepeg 0.4 mg Tablet:**

Weight of 20 tablets = 2.7280 gm

Average weight of tablet = $2.7280 / 20 = 0.1364$ gm
=136.4 mg

Assay results of Selepeg 0.4 mg Tablet:

Sample	Area	% Assay	Mean Assay
Sample 1	5322036	97.38	98.32
Sample 2	5430523	99.26	

Table no.11. Assay results of Selepeg 0.4 mg Tablet

Sample Name: TABLET SAMPLE SOLUTION 1

VWD: Signal A, 298 nm Results

Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Selezipag	2.94	5322036	1.24	9641
Totals		5322036		

Fig. No. 8 Typical chromatogram Selepeg 0.4 mg Tablet sample.

Acceptance criteria:

1) % Assay found should be in the range of 90-110%.

Data interpretation:

From the above results, it can be concluded that the assay result is within the limit for selected marketed test sample and sample can be used for validation.

Results of Filter study

Sample description	Area	% Absolute difference
Unfiltered	5368256	NA
0.45 μ PVDF filter	5335630	0.61
0.45 μ Nylon filter	5348925	0.36

Table no.12. Results of Filter study

VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD**FILTRATION STUDY:**

Filtration study of an analytical procedure checks the interference of extraneous components from filter, deposition on filter bed and compatibility of filter with sample. Performed on tablet test sample.

Chromatograms:

Sample Name: SAMPLE UNFILTERED

VWD: Signal A,
298 nm Results

Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Selexipag	2.94	5368256	1.24	9676
Totals		5368256		

Fig. No. 9 Typical chromatogram of unfiltered sample.

Sample Name: SAMPLE PVDF FILTER

VWD: Signal A,
298 nm Results

Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Selexipag	2.93	5335630	1.21	9475
Totals		5335630		

Fig. No. 10 Typical chromatogram of sample filtered through 0.45µm PVDF filter.

Sample Name: SAMPLE NYLON FILTER

VWD: Signal A,
298 nm Results

Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Selexipag	2.93	5348925	1.23	9580
Totals		5348925		

Fig. No. 11 Typical chromatogram of sample filtered through 0.45 µm Nylon filter.

Acceptance criteria: % Absolute difference of filtered samples NMT 2.0 w.r.t. Unfiltered sample.

Data interpretation: Both filters PVDF and Nylon passes the criteria for filter study, hence both filters can be used. We used PVDF filter because it showed less absolute difference as compare to Nylon filter.

SOLUTION STABILITY: Stability study was conducted for Standard as well as Test Sample. Stability study was performed at normal laboratory conditions. The solution was stored at normal illuminated laboratory conditions and analyzed at initial, after 12 hours and 24 hours.

Results of Solution stability.

Sample solution			Standard solution		
Time point	Area	% Absolute difference	Time point	Area	% Absolute difference
Initial	5418256	NA	Initial	5482501	NA
12 Hours	5378021	0.74	12 Hours	5446090	0.66
24 Hours	5361080	1.06	24 Hours	5438340	0.81

Table no.13. Results of Solution stability.

Chromatograms:

Fig. No. 12 Typical chromatogram of Standard solution Initial.

Fig. No. 13 Typical chromatogram of Standard solution After 24 Hrs.

Fig. No. 14 Typical chromatogram of Test solution Initial.

Fig. No. 15 Typical chromatogram of Test solution After 24 Hrs

Acceptance criteria: % Absolute difference of Stability solution: NMT 2.0 w.r.t. Initial solution.

of components which may be expected to be present.

Data interpretation: Standard and Test solution was found stable up to 24 Hrs. Hence both solutions can be used up to 24 Hrs.

Blank & Placebo solution prepared and injected to check interference at R.T. of Selexipag.

Results of Specificity.

1) **SPECIFICITY:** Specificity is the ability to access unequivocally the analyte in the presence

Description	Observation
Blank	No interference at R.T. of Selexipag due to blank
Placebo	No interference at R.T. of Selexipag due to placebo

Table no.14. Results of Specificity.

Chromatograms:**Fig. No. 17 Typical chromatogram of Placebo solution.****Acceptance criteria:**

Blank: There should be no Interference at R.T. of Selexipag.

Placebo: There should be no Interference at R.T. of Selexipag.

Data interpretation: Blank and placebo was not having interference at R.T. of Selexipag. Hence

developed chromatographic method passed the criteria for specificity.

2) Linearity and Range

Linearity of an analytical method is its ability to elicit test results that are proportional to the concentration of analyte in samples within a given range.

Linearity Data for Selexipag:

Level	Conc ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Area	Mean	% RSD
10%	0.50	536625	536641	0.083
		536205		
		537094		
50%	2.50	2754025	2753733	0.095

		2750971		
		2756203		
100%	5.00	5470940	5473144	0.105
		5479692		
		5468800		
125%	6.25	6839103	6837310	0.088
		6842236		
		6830590		
150%	7.50	8166929	8164694	0.090
		8156463		
		8170690		

Table no.15. Linearity Data for Selexipag:

Fig. No. 18 Calibration curve of Selexipag

Data of linearity of Selexipag:

Sr no.	Parameter	Result value	Acceptance criteria
1	Beer's linearity range	0.50-7.50 µg/mL	NA
2	Correlation coefficient (R ²)	0.99998	NLT 0.98
3	Intercept	10423.03727	To be report
4	Slope	1090271.578	To be report
5	% RSD for area at each level	NA	NMT 2.0

Table no.16. Data of linearity of Selexipag

The respective linear equation for Selexipag was:

X = concentration of Analyte in µg/mL

$$Y = M X + C$$

Y = is area of peak.

$$Y = 1090271.578 X + 10423.03727$$

M = Slope

Where,

C= Intercept

Chromatograms:

Sample Name: LINEARITY 10%_1

VWD: Signal A,
298 nm Results

Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Selexipag	2.92	536625	1.25	10114
Totals		536625		

Fig. No. 19 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 10%.

Sample Name: LINEARITY 50%_1

VWD: Signal A,
298 nm Results

Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Selexipag	2.92	2754025	1.23	9678
Totals		2754025		

Fig. No. 20 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 50%.

Sample Name: LINEARITY 100%_1

VWD: Signal A,
298 nm Results

Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Selexipag	2.94	5470940	1.22	9556
Totals		5470940		

Fig. No. 21 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 100%.

Fig. No. 22 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 125%.

Fig. No. 23 Typical chromatogram of Linearity 150%.

CONCLUSION:

From the calibration curve it was concluded that the Selexipag shows linear response in the range of 0.50-7.50 µg/ml. The Regression value was found well within the limit.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ):

$\sigma = 19216.96681$ (Residual standard deviation of a regression line)

$s = 1090271.578$ (Slope)

Detection limit (LOD):

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \sigma / S$$

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times 19216.96681 / 1090271.578$$

$$\text{LOD} = 0.058 \mu\text{g/mL}$$

Quantitation limit (LOQ):

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma / S$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times 19216.96681 / 1090271.578$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 0.176 \mu\text{g/ML}$$

1) ACCURACY (RECOVERY):

The accuracy of an analytical method is the closeness of test results obtained by that method to the true value. The accuracy of an analytical method is determined by applying the method to analyzed samples to which known amounts of analyte have been added.

Result and statistical data of Accuracy of Selexipag

Level (%)	Area	Recovered conc (µg/mL)	Added conc (µg/mL)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery	% RSD
50	2770025	2.53	2.50	101.20	99.87	1.2236
	2725764	2.49	2.50	99.60		
	2701276	2.47	2.50	98.80		
100	5396401	4.93	5.00	98.60	99.13	0.5077
	5446456	4.98	5.00	99.60		
	5420073	4.96	5.00	99.20		
150	8117807	7.42	7.50	98.93	99.64	0.6336
	8186973	7.49	7.50	99.87		
	8208060	7.51	7.50	100.13		

Table no.17. Result and statistical data of Accuracy of Selexipag

Overall Recovery: 99.55 %

% RSD for Overall Recovery: 0.805

Chromatograms:

Fig. No. 24 Typical chromatogram of Accuracy 50%.

Fig. No. 25 Typical chromatogram of Accuracy 100%.

Fig. No. 26 Typical chromatogram of Accuracy 150%.

Acceptance criteria:

% Recovery for each level and overall recovery: 98.0 to 102.0%

% RSD for each level and overall recovery: NMT 2.0

Data interpretation: Recovery of analytical procedure was found well within acceptance criteria at all 3 levels. % Recovery not gets hampered by changed in analyte concentration.

PRECISION

Precision of an analytical method is the degree of agreement among individual test results when the procedure is applied repeatedly to multiple samplings of a homogenous sample. Precision of an analytical method is usually expressed as standard deviation or relative standard deviation. Precision was performed on Test sample.

Result of Intra- day and Inter- Day Precision for Selexipag test sample assay:

	Sample	Test Sample (mg)	Area	% Assay	
Repeatability	Sample 1	682.6	5401569	98.70	
	Sample 2	683.2	5343452	97.56	
	Sample 3	682.4	5380045	98.34	
	Sample 4	682.8	5441206	99.40	
	Sample 5	683.3	5304315	96.83	
	Sample 6	682.2	5516430	100.86	
	Mean				98.62
	STD DEV				1.416923
	% RSD				1.437
	Intermediate precision (Inter-Day)	Sample 1	682.5	5349253	97.76
Sample 2		681.8	5480058	100.25	
Sample 3		682.4	5528912	101.06	
Sample 4		682.7	5410181	98.85	
Sample 5		683.2	5438222	99.29	
Sample 6		682.6	5352410	97.80	

	Mean	99.17
	STD DEV	1.320627
	% RSD	1.332
Repeatability Plus Inter-day	Mean	98.892
	STD DEV	1.33747
	% RSD	1.352

Table no.18. Result of Intra- day and Inter- Day Precision for Selexipag test sample assay

Chromatograms:

Sample Name: PRECISION SAMPLE 1

VWD: Signal A,
298 nm Results

Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Selexipag	2.92	5401569	1.21	9450
Totals		5401569		

Fig. No. 27 Typical chromatogram of Repeatability precision (Sample 1).

Sample Name: INTER MEDIATE PRECISION SAMPLE 1

VWD: Signal A,
298 nm Results

Name	Retention Time	Area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates (USP)
Selexipag	2.92	5349253	1.24	9663
Totals		5349253		

Fig. No. 28 Typical chromatogram of Inter-day precision (Sample 1).

Acceptance criteria:

% Assay: % Assay value for each sample (Individual sample) and mean assay value for precision (6 sample), mean assay value intermediate precision (6 sample), and mean assay value for precision plus intermediate precision sample (12 samples): 90-110%

% RSD: % RSD for precision study samples (6 sample), Intermediate precision study samples (6 samples) and precision plus intermediate precision sample (12 samples): NMT 2.0

Data interpretation: % Assay and % RSD was found well within acceptance limit and hence method is precise (Reproducible).

3) ROBUSTNESS:

The robustness of an analytical method is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage.

Following changes made under Robustness:

- Change in Wavelength
- Change in flow rate
- Change in column oven temperature

Result of Robustness study:

Change in Parameter	R.T.	Standard area	Asymmetry	Theoretical plates
Wavelength by +3 NM (229 NM)	2.94	5239583	1.23	9703
Wavelength by -3 NM (223 NM)	2.95	5160078	1.21	9426
Flow rate by +10% (1.1 mL/min)	2.68	5340607	1.20	9233
Flow rate by -10% (0.9 mL/min)	3.28	5320610	1.24	9745
Column oven temp by +2°C (37 °C)	2.94	5531080	1.21	9366
Column oven temp by -2°C (33 °C)	2.94	5516972	1.25	9714

Table no.19. Result of Robustness study of selexipag

Chromatograms:**Change in Wavelength by +3 NM:**

Fig. No. 29 Typical chromatogram of Standard +3 NM.

A. Change in Wavelength by -3 NM:**Fig. No. 32 Typical chromatogram of Standard -10 F.R.%.**

D. Change in Column Oven temperature by +2°C:**Fig. No. 34 Typical chromatogram of Standard -2°C C.O.T.****Acceptance criteria:**

Chromatography (System suitability) acceptance criteria should not get failed.

Data interpretation: From the above results, it was concluded that the system suitability test result was found well within the limits and analytical method was robust.

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